

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE INTERNATIONAL COVENANT ON ECONOMIC, SOCIAL AND CULTURAL RIGHTS AND SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND ADEQUATE FOOD

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Abstract

In order to develop this article, a documentary review of the elaboration and production of studies related to the relationship between the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights with Social Responsibility and Adequate Food was carried out to know, through a bibliometric study of the main characteristics of 36 publications registered in the Scopus database. The results obtained from this database were organized in tables and figures, categorizing the information by variables such as Year of Publication, Country of Origin and Area of Knowledge, which allowed to identify, through qualitative analysis, the position of different authors regarding the proposed topic. The main findings of this research were that the United States stood out for having the highest scientific production, leading the list with 8 publications. Likewise, the area of knowledge that contributed the most to the construction of bibliographic material related to the study of variables was the Social Sciences, with 28 published documents.

Keywords: Convention or Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Social Responsibility, Adequate Food, Cooperation.

1. Introduction

Maintaining a healthy diet seems important for current generations, who seek to acquire the necessary nutrients and vitamins through natural foods that contribute to the optimal maintenance of human health, avoiding diseases, allowing reproduction and prolonging their life cycle. However, little seems to be known about the term Adequate Food, its relationship with the Convention on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, and the importance of Social Responsibility in achieving it.

The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) “constitutes the principal universal instrument setting forth the rights and obligations for Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ESCR). It provides for progressive realization and considers the restrictions due to resource constraints” (OHCHR, n.d.). Although this Convention is based on the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the former emphasizes the need to guarantee the exercise of second-generation rights, such as the right to work, health, education and food, which aim to achieve equality in a given territory.

In the specific case of the right to food, it results from the right to an adequate standard of living and consists of two dimensions that promote access to food from the monetary aspect and its availability in the territory and the absorption of calories, proteins and everything necessary for adequate food in a progressive manner. This depends entirely on the different actors’ efforts and their degree of Social Responsibility. According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), Social Responsibility can be defined as follows:

Responsibility of an organization for the impacts that its decisions and activities have on society and the environment through ethical and transparent behavior that:

- contribute to sustainable development, including the health and well-being of society;
- take into consideration the expectations of your stakeholders;
- complies with applicable law and is consistent with international standards of behavior; and
- is integrated throughout the organization and is put into practice in its relationships (ISO, n.d.).

To better understand the relationship between our variables, this article seeks to describe the main characteristics of the set of publications in the Scopus database about them, as well as to describe the position of certain authors affiliated with institutions around the world.

2. General Objective

To analyze from a bibliometric and bibliographic perspective, the elaboration of research papers on the variables Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Social Responsibility and Adequate Food in Scopus.

3. Methodology

This article is conducted through a mixed research approach combining quantitative and qualitative methods.

On the one hand, a quantitative analysis of the information selected in Scopus is carried out under a bibliometric approach of the scientific production corresponding to the study of the relationship between the variables Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Social Responsibility and Adequate Food in Scopus.

On the other hand, from a qualitative perspective, examples of some research works published in the area of the study mentioned above are analyzed from a bibliographic approach that allows describing the position of different authors on the proposed topic.

It is important to note that the entire search was conducted through Scopus, establishing the parameters referenced in *Figure 1*.

3.1 Methodological design

Figure 1. Methodological design

Source: Own elaboration

3.1.1 Phase 1: Data Collection

The data collection was executed from the Search tool on the Scopus web page, where 36 publications were obtained from the choice of the following filters:

TITLE-ABS-KEY (international AND covenant AND on AND economic, AND social AND cultural AND rights, AND social AND responsibility)

- ❖ Published documents whose study variables are related to Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Social Responsibility and Adequate Food.
- ❖ No time limit.
- ❖ No country limit.
- ❖ Without distinction of area of knowledge.
- ❖ Without distinction of type of publication.

3.1.2 Phase 2: Construction of analysis material

The information collected in Scopus during the previous phase is organized and subsequently classified through graphs, figures and tables as follows:

- ❖ Word Co-occurrence.
- ❖ Year of publication
- ❖ Country of origin of the publication.
- ❖ Knowledge area.
- ❖ Type of Publication

3.1.3 Phase 3: Drafting conclusions and final document

In this phase, the study proceeds with analyzing the results previously obtained, resulting in the determination of conclusions and, consequently, the final document.

4. Results

4.1 Cooccurrence of words

Figure 2 shows the co-occurrence of keywords found in the publications identified in the Scopus database.

The interest in knowing the relationship between the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights with Social Responsibility and Adequate Food dates back to the last century, since 1994, when 1 related document was published. In general, Figure 3 shows a constant fluctuation in scientific production where there are years with no participation and others with greater involvement, and such is the case of 2015, which reached the highest peak in the graph with a total of 15 publications.

The texts published in 2014 include the article entitled “A modern integrated paradigm for international responsibility arising from violations of economic, social and cultural right” (Desierto & Gillespie, 2014), which focuses its study on the responsibilities acquired by state and non-state actors since the ratification of the Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and the control mechanisms established by the Covenant committee to ensure their compliance taking into account the following premises or “general obligation” (Desierto & Gillespie, 2014):

‘Non-discrimination principle,’ which requires a State Party to ensure non-discrimination in its implementation of Covenant rights; and the ‘non-regression principle,’ which commits a State Party to conduct of social protection that, at a minimum, will not fall below its previously committed legal baseline of the ‘minimum core’ of Covenant rights (Desierto & Gillespie, 2014).

Concluding that despite the differences that may exist between states, the committee, over time, was able to maintain control over human rights compliance giving rise to a “modern interpretive paradigm for the authoritative determination of international responsibility for violations of the Covenant” (Desierto & Gillespie, 2014).

4.3 Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of scientific production according to the nationality of the authors.

Figure 4. *Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.*

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

In the study of the relationship between the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and Social Accountability and Adequate Food, the United States leads the list of published documents with a total of 8 records in the Scopus database, followed by the United Kingdom and South Africa, with 7 and 5 texts respectively. An example is an article entitled “The Right to Food: Holding Global Actors Accountable under International Law”, which “argues that the right to food is a fundamental human right” and that international law needs to be rethought under globalization” for three purposes (Narula, 2006). First, to establish a legal framework based on globalization to hold non-state actors accountable for the impact of non-compliance with the right

to food. Second, to “respect and protect” the right to food (Narula, 2006), without territorial limits, including the monitoring of non-state organizations under their control. Third, to consider the relocation of the right to food as a “customary international right” to ensure its compliance from any state (Narula, 2006), regardless of whether or not it has ratified the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights.

At this point, it is important to note that the elaboration of scientific publications, in many cases, is based on collaborations that may involve private and public institutions from one or several countries. Therefore, the same publication may be linked to one or more authors with different nationalities and thus to more than one country simultaneously, making part of each of the total number of articles or publications in the final sum.

Figure 5. Co-citations between countries.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Figure 5 shows the research grouping according to the collaboration between authors from different international institutions. Again, there is outstanding participation among authors affiliated with institutions in countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, South Africa, Australia and Belgium.

4.4 Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge

Figure 6 shows the distribution of the production of scientific publications according to the area of knowledge through which the different research methodologies are implemented.

Figure 6. Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Due to the impact of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights on the Social Responsibility and Adequate Food of any state or organization, the social sciences is the area where most documents related to our variables are produced and subsequently published in the Scopus database. Other areas such as medicine, arts and humanities and economics/finance have also contributed to the study of these variables, publishing 7, 3 and 2 papers, respectively.

As can be seen in *Figure 6*, the variables object of this study is relevant in several areas of knowledge since they directly influence the health of the members of society, while they depend on the economic capabilities of each organization and state in the procurement of food products that guarantee the Adequate Nutrition of its citizens.

4.5 Type of publication

Figure 7 shows the distribution of the bibliographic findings according to the type of publication made by each of the authors found in Scopus.

Figure 7. Type of publication

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Figure 7 clearly shows that the predominant type of publication in the study was the journal article, with a total of 18 documents. In second place are book chapters or sections with 14, followed by reviews with only 4 publications each.

The book sections include the title “Shared Responsibility for the Right to Health (Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights)” (Hammonds & Ooms, 2013), which highlights the need to “identify and create global mechanisms to ensure that the rights of all people are guaranteed, which implies accepting a shared global responsibility for the right” (Hammonds & Ooms, 2013), referring to the importance of monitoring and assistance provided extraterritorially, as well as the use of cooperation to achieve better results by state and non-state actors, who directly influence the fulfillment of basic rights such as the right to health, thus concluding that international agreements must comply with the international human rights obligations of States parties and the potential of the Optional Protocol to enhance accountability and respect for human rights globally” (Hammonds & Ooms, 2013).

5. Conclusions

Finally, thanks to the bibliometric analysis carried out in this research work, it was possible to establish that the United States was the country with the largest number of published records regarding the variables International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights with a total of 8 publications in the Scopus database. Likewise, it was determined that journal articles lead the

type of publication with 18 texts and that the social sciences was the area with the largest number of studies concerning the subject in the years mentioned above.

On the other hand, it should be noted that most of the documents analyzed share a common interest in the strategies or alternatives used by the Committee of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights to monitor and then penalize, where necessary, those actors who have not made sufficient effort to provide their individuals with access to these second-generation rights. Cooperation and globalization are undoubtedly tools that allow organizations to comply with the covenant, which, when well executed, strengthens the degree of Social Responsibility.

On the other hand, it was determined that to achieve the access of an entire nation to Adequate Food, state and non-state organizations, including financial institutions, must work together, taking into account the need to ensure the procurement of products necessary for good nutrition from the availability of the same and obtaining sufficient monetary resources to enable their purchase. Likewise, it is of utmost relevance the promotion of Adequate Nutrition through promotion programs developed by the health system and public policies.

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